

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On Certain Applications via (φ, \wp) -Suzuki type Fixed Point Results in A_b -Metric Spaces

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Abstract

Objective: In this study, we establish the existence and uniqueness of the common coupled fixed point theorem on complete A_b -metric space. **Method:** We have used the (φ, \wp) -type Suzuki contraction on two mappings. **Findings:** For two mappings on the complete A_b -Metric Space, we were able to obtain and prove a unique common coupled fixed point theorem and justify it with a suitable example. **Novelty:** A unique common coupled fixed point is obtained by using (φ, \wp) -type Suzuki contraction on two mappings and application of Suzuki contractive fixed point solutions of (φ, \wp) -type to integral equations in the setup of A_b -Metric Space.

Subject classification for mathematics in 2000. 54E50, 47H10, and 54H25.**Keywords:** A_b -Metric Space; (φ, \wp) -Type Suzuki Contraction; ω -Compatible; A_b -Completeness; Coupled Fixed Point

1 Introduction

A stunning fusion of geometry, topology, and analysis is seen in fixed point theory. Due to its numerous applications in approximation theory, non-linear analysis, medical innovation, biomechanics, integral, and impulsive differential equations, problem solving, homotopy theory, and algorithms, it has been playing a significant role.

Generalized versions of the core discoveries of Banach and Edelstein were recently shown by Suzuki⁽¹⁾ which sparked a great deal of interest in this area⁽²⁻⁴⁾. The notion of b-Metric Space (MS) was proposed⁽⁵⁾ in 1989. Later, many authors generalized this and introduced the new Metric Space. M. Abbas et al.⁽⁶⁾ presented the idea of n-tuple Metric Space and examined its topological characteristics in 2015. A_b -Metric Space is a generalized version of n-tuple Metric Space, as first proposed by M. Ughade et al.⁽⁷⁾. Then, in partially ordered A_b -MS, K. Ravibabu et al.⁽⁸⁾ obtained unique coupled common fixed point (UCCFP) theorems. Guo and Lakshmikantham⁽⁹⁾ generated the notion of a coupled fixed point (CFP) in 1987. Later, Bhaskar and Lakshmikantham⁽¹⁰⁾ employing a weak contractive type assumption, established a novel fixed point theorem for a mixed monotone mapping on a Metric Space equipped with partial order. Several authors⁽¹¹⁻¹⁶⁾ studied the coupled fixed-point results.

This paper is to provide unique coupled common fixed point theorems in the set-up of A_b -Metric Space for (φ, \wp) -type contractions and (φ, \wp) -type Suzuki contractive mapping. Additionally, we can provide appropriate examples and an application to integral equations.

2 Methodology

This section includes a few definitions, examples, and lemmas that are necessary to provide our primary findings.

Definition 2.1 ⁽⁷⁾: Consider \mathfrak{J} as a non-empty set, & $\vartheta \geq 1$ as a real number. An A_b -metric on \mathfrak{J} is defined as a mapping $\tilde{n}_b : \mathfrak{J}^n \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ that meets the following constraints for every $\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{y} \in I$
 $z = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

$$(\tilde{n}_b 1) \quad \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{x}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}_n) \geq 0$$

$$(\tilde{n}_b 2) \quad \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{x}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}_n) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathfrak{x}_1 = \mathfrak{x}_2 = \dots = \mathfrak{x}_{n-1} = \mathfrak{x}_n$$

$$(\tilde{n}_b 3) \quad \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{x}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}_n) \leq \vartheta \left(\begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{x}_1, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_1)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \\ + \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_2, \mathfrak{x}_2, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_2)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \\ + \dots + \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}_{n-1}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_{n-1})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \\ + \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_n, \mathfrak{x}_n, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_n)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \end{array} \right)$$

Then $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ is called an A_b - Metric Space

Definition 2.2 ⁽⁷⁾: A metric space $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ is symmetric if

$$\tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) = \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{y}, \mathfrak{y}, \dots, (\mathfrak{y})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}) \forall \mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{y} \in \mathfrak{J}$$

Definition 2.3 ⁽⁷⁾: Let $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ denote a A_b -Metric Space Then, if $\mathfrak{x} \in \mathfrak{J}, \delta > 0$, we define the open ball $B\tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \delta)$ and closed ball $B\tilde{n}_b [\mathfrak{x}, \delta]$ with center \mathfrak{x} and radius δ as follows:

$$B\tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \delta) = \{ \mathfrak{y} \in \mathfrak{J} : \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{y}, \mathfrak{y}, \dots, (\mathfrak{y})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}) < \delta \}, \text{ and}$$

$$B\tilde{n}_b [\mathfrak{x}, \delta] = \{ \mathfrak{y} \in \mathfrak{J} : \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{y}, \mathfrak{y}, \dots, (\mathfrak{y})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}) \leq \delta \}.$$

Lemma 2.4 ⁽⁷⁾: In a A_b -Metric Space, we have

$$1. \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \leq \vartheta \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{y}, \mathfrak{y}, \dots, (\mathfrak{y})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x})$$

$$2. \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \leq \vartheta (n-1) \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{y}, \mathfrak{y}, \dots, (\mathfrak{y})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y})$$

Definition 2.5 ⁽⁷⁾: Let $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be a Metric Space. A sequence $\{\mathfrak{x}_z\}$ in \mathfrak{J} is defined as follows:

1. If $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that $\tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}_1) < \delta$ to every $l, z \geq n_0$ then $\{\mathfrak{x}_z\}$ is \tilde{n}_b - Cauchy sequence.

2. We denote $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{x}_z = \mathfrak{x}$. \tilde{n}_b convergent to the point $\mathfrak{x} \in \mathfrak{J}$ if, $\forall \epsilon > 0$ there exists a positive integer n_0 such that

$$\tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{x}) < \epsilon \text{ to every } z \geq n_0$$

3. In a metric space $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ if all \tilde{n}_b - Cauchy sequences in \mathfrak{J} are \tilde{n}_b -convergent, then A_b is said to be complete.

Lemma 2.6: Assuming that $\{\mathfrak{x}_k\}$ is \tilde{n}_b -convergent to \mathfrak{x} and $\{\mathfrak{y}_k\}$ is \tilde{n}_b -convergent to \mathfrak{y} & $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ is the A_b -metric space with $\vartheta \geq 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad \frac{1}{\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) &\leq \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}_z) \\ &\leq \limsup_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}_z) \\ &\leq \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \end{aligned}$$

In particular, if $\mathfrak{y}_z = \mathfrak{y}$ is a constant, then

$$\begin{aligned} (ii) \quad \frac{1}{\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) &\leq \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \\ &\leq \limsup_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z, \dots, (\mathfrak{x}_z)_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \\ &\leq \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b (\mathfrak{x}, \mathfrak{x}, \dots, (\mathfrak{x})_{n-1}, \mathfrak{y}) \end{aligned}$$

We consider the following to obtain our results.

3 Results and Discussion

Definition 3.1: Assume $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be the A_b -Metric Space, a mapping $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$. Then (α, α) is referred to as a coupled fixed point of F if $F(\alpha, \alpha) = \alpha$, $F(\alpha, \alpha) = \alpha$, for $\alpha, \alpha \in \mathfrak{J}$

Definition 3.2: Assume that $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ and $f : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ be two mappings where $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ is the A_b -Metric space

1. If $F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha$, $F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha$, then an element (α, α) is considered a coupled coincident point of F & f

2. A Coupled common point of F & f is defined as an element (α, α) if

$$F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha = \alpha, F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha = \alpha,$$

3. If $f(F(\alpha, \alpha)) = F(f\alpha, f\alpha)$ and $F(f\alpha, f\alpha) = F(f\alpha, f\alpha)$ then for all $\alpha, \alpha \in \mathfrak{J}$, then there exists a pair $(F, f) \ni F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha$, $F(\alpha, \alpha) = f\alpha$ then (F, f) is called ω -compatible

Definition 3.3: $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be a A_b -metric space & $F : \mathfrak{J} \times \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ & $f : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ be two mappings

(i₀) The pair (F, f) is supposed to be a (φ, φ) -type contraction, if there exist two functions $\varphi \in \Theta$ & $\varphi \in \Omega$ such that

$$\forall \alpha, \alpha, \beta, d \in \mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\alpha, \alpha), \dots, F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\beta, d)) > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\alpha, \alpha), \dots, F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\beta, d)) \right) \leq \varphi(M(\alpha, \alpha, \beta, d)) - \varphi(M(\alpha, \alpha, \beta, d)) \tag{3.1}$$

(i₁) The pair (F, f) is supposed to be a (φ, φ) -type Suzuki contraction, if There exists two functions $\varphi \in \Theta$ and $\varphi \in \Omega$ such that $\forall, \alpha, \alpha, \beta, d \in I$ with $F(\alpha, \alpha) \neq f\alpha, F(\alpha, \alpha) \neq f\alpha$ and $f\alpha \neq f\alpha$

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, F(\alpha, \alpha)) \leq \max \left(\begin{matrix} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, f\beta), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, fd), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, (f\beta)_{n-1}, F(\beta, d)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, (fd)_{n-1}, F(d, \beta)) \end{matrix} \right) \text{ implies}$$

$$\varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\alpha, \alpha), \dots, F(\alpha, \alpha), F(\beta, d)) \right) \leq \varphi(M(\alpha, \alpha, \beta, d)) - \varphi(M(\alpha, \alpha, \beta, d)) \tag{3.2}$$

Where

$$M(\alpha, \alpha, \beta, d) = \max \left(\begin{matrix} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, f\beta), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, fd), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, F(\alpha, \alpha)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, F(\alpha, \alpha)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, (f\beta)_{n-1}, F(\beta, d)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, (fd)_{n-1}, F(d, \beta)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, (f\beta)_{n-1}, F(\alpha, \alpha)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, (fd)_{n-1}, F(\alpha, \alpha)), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, F(\beta, d)), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, (f\alpha)_{n-1}, F(d, \beta)) \end{matrix} \right)$$

And $\Omega = \{\varphi/\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)\}$ & $\Theta = \{\varphi/\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)\}$ are the functions satisfying the following conditions.

(i₀) φ is continuous, monotonically non-decreasing, and φ is lower semi-continuous.

(i₁) $\varphi(t) = 0 = \varphi(t)$ if and only if $t = 0$

Lemma 3.4: Assume that $\{\alpha_z\}$ is a sequence in \mathfrak{J} such that $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha_z, \alpha_z, \dots, \alpha_{z+1}) = 0$

Let $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be a A_b -Metric Space with coefficient $\vartheta \geq 1$. There exist $\epsilon > 0$ & two sequences say $\{\alpha_{w_k}\}$ & $\{\alpha_{z_k}\}$ of positive integers such that the below instances hold if $\{\alpha_z\}$ is not a ϑ_b -Cauchy sequence

$$(i) \ 0 \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha_{w_k}, \alpha_{w_k}, \dots, \alpha_{z_k}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha_{w_k}, \alpha_{w_k}, \dots, \alpha_{z_k}) \leq (n-1) \vartheta^0$$

$$(ii) \ \frac{0}{(n-1)\vartheta} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha_{w_{k+1}}, \alpha_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \alpha_{z_k}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha_{w_{k+1}}, \alpha_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \alpha_{z_k}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^2$$

$$(iii) \frac{\overset{\circ}{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^2 \overset{\circ}{0}$$

$$(iv) \frac{\overset{\circ}{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^4 \overset{\circ}{0}$$

Proof. Suppose $\{\mathfrak{a}_z\}$ is not a \tilde{n}_b -Cauchy sequence, then there exists an $\epsilon > 0$ & two sequences $\{\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}\}$ & $\{\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}\}$ (say) of positive integers such that $z_k > w_k > k$,

$$\tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}) < \overset{\circ}{0} \text{ and } \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \geq \overset{\circ}{0} \tag{3.3}$$

Using the fact that $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z+1}) = 0$ and (Equation (3.3)), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{0} \leq \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \\ &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \overset{\circ}{0} + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, we have that

$$\overset{\circ}{0} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \leq (n-1)\vartheta \overset{\circ}{0}$$

Moreover, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \overset{\circ}{0} &\leq \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \\ &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \\ &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}) + (n-1)\vartheta^3 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \\ &\quad + \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \quad \text{and} \\ \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \\ &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}) + (n-1)\vartheta^3 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \\ &\quad + \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \\ &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}) + (n-1)^2 \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}) \\ &\quad + (n-1)\vartheta^5 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) + \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

By considering the lower limit in the first inequality as $k \rightarrow \infty$, the upper limit in the second inequality as $k \rightarrow \infty$ we arrive at

$$\frac{\overset{\circ}{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^4 \overset{\circ}{0}$$

Additionally, we have that

$$\overset{\circ}{0} \leq \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})$$

And

$$\tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k+1}}) \\ &\leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k-1}}) + \vartheta^3 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{z_{k-1}}, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k-1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}) \\ &+ \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k+1}}) \end{aligned}$$

We also have that

$$\frac{\dot{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_k}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_{k+1}}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^2 \dot{0}$$

Applying a comparable method, we determine that

$$\frac{\dot{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta} \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}) \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{x}_{w_{k+1}}, \mathfrak{x}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, \mathfrak{x}_{z_k}) \leq (n-1)^2 \vartheta^2 \dot{0}.$$

Theorem 3.5: Let $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be a A_b -Metric Space and $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ & $f : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ be two mappings that satisfy (φ, \wp) -type Suzuki contraction with

- a) $F(\mathfrak{J}^2) \subseteq f(\mathfrak{J})$ & $f(\mathfrak{J})$ is complete,
- b) The pair (F, f) right is ω -compatible.

Then there is unique coupled common fixed point of F & f in \mathfrak{J}

Proof: Suppose $\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0 \in \mathfrak{J}$, then from (a), we establish the sequences $\{\mathfrak{x}_z\}, \{\mathfrak{c}_z\}$ in \mathfrak{J} as

$$F(\mathfrak{x}_z, \mathfrak{c}_z) = f\mathfrak{x}_{z+1}, F(\mathfrak{c}_z, \mathfrak{x}_z) = f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1} \text{ where } z = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Case (i): Assume that

$$f\mathfrak{x}_z \neq f\mathfrak{x}_{z+1} \text{ or } f\mathfrak{c}_z \neq f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1} \forall z. \tag{3.4}$$

Since,

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, F(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0)) = \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1) \\ &\leq \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1) \\ &\leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_0, f\mathfrak{c}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, F(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_0, f\mathfrak{c}_0, \dots, F(\mathfrak{c}_0, \mathfrak{x}_0)), \end{array} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Then from (Equation (3.2)), we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_1, f\mathfrak{x}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_2)) = \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0), F(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0), \dots, F(\mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{c}_1))) \\ &\leq \wp(M(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0, \mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{c}_1)) - \wp(M(\mathfrak{x}_0, \mathfrak{c}_0, \mathfrak{x}_1, \mathfrak{c}_1)) \leq \wp \left(\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_0, f\mathfrak{c}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_1, f\mathfrak{x}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_2), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_1, f\mathfrak{c}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_2) \end{array} \right\} \right) - \\ &\varphi \left(\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_0, f\mathfrak{c}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_1, f\mathfrak{x}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_2), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_1, f\mathfrak{c}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_2) \end{array} \right\} \right) \\ &\leq \varphi \left(\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_0, f\mathfrak{x}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_0, f\mathfrak{c}_0, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_1), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{x}_1, f\mathfrak{x}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{x}_2), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_1, f\mathfrak{c}_1, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_2) \end{array} \right\} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Because of

$$\begin{aligned}
 M(\alpha_0, \alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_1) &= \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, F(\alpha_0, \alpha_0)), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, F(\alpha_0, \alpha_0)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, F(\alpha_1, \alpha_1)), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, F(\alpha_1, \alpha_1)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, F(\alpha_0, \alpha_0)), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, F(\alpha_0, \alpha_0)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, F(\alpha_1, \alpha_1)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, F(\alpha_1, \alpha_1)), \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 \text{From definition of } \varphi, \text{ we have}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3.5}$$

Similarly, we can prove that

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3.6}$$

From (Equations (3.5) and (3.6)) one can conclude

$$\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3.7}$$

If $\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \leq \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\}$.

Then from (Equation (3.7)), we have

$$\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\}$$

This is a contradiction. Hence, from (Equation (3.7)), we have

$$\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_1, f\alpha_1, \dots, f\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1) \end{aligned} \right\}.$$

Continuing in this way, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\alpha_{z+1}), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\alpha_{z+1}) \end{aligned} \right\} &\leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z-1}, f\alpha_{z-1}, \dots, f\alpha_z), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z-1}, f\alpha_{z-1}, \dots, f\alpha_z) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{((n-1)^3\vartheta^6)^2} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z-2}, f\alpha_{z-2}, \dots, f\alpha_{z-1}), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z-2}, f\alpha_{z-2}, \dots, f\alpha_{z-1}) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{((n-1)^3\vartheta^6)^p} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_0, f\alpha_0, \dots, f\alpha_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } z \rightarrow \infty
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\alpha_{z+1}) = 0 \text{ and } \lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\alpha_{z+1}) = 0 \tag{3.8}$$

The \tilde{n}_b -cauchy sequence $\{f\mathfrak{a}_z\}$ will now be demonstrated. Assuming that $\{f\mathfrak{a}_z\}$ is not a \tilde{n}_b -Cauchy sequence, then $\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \geq \epsilon$ and sequences of positive integers $\{z_k\}$ and $\{w_k\}$ where $z_k \geq w_k \geq k$. We can select $\{z_k\}$ as the smallest positive integer for each $k > 0$, corresponding to w_k such that $\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}) \geq \epsilon$. We can select $z_0 \in N \cup \{0\}$ such that $\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k-1}}) < \epsilon$

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})) < \frac{\epsilon}{n\vartheta^2} < \epsilon \leq \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k})$$

$$\leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})) \end{array} \right\}.$$

Then, from (Equation (3.2)), we can get

$$\wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}})) = \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}), F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}), \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})))$$

$$\leq \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})) - \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})) \tag{3.9}$$

Where $M(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})$

$$= \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k})), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}) \end{array} \right\}$$

Using (Equation (3.4)) and (Equation (3.8)), we have that

$$\overset{\circ}{0} \leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} M(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{a}_{z_k})$$

$$= \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\leq \{(n-1)\vartheta^0, (n-1)\vartheta^0, 0, 0, 0, 0, (n-1)^2\vartheta^3, (n-1)^2\vartheta^3\} = (n-1)^2\vartheta^3 \overset{\circ}{0}$$

So that by using (Equation (3.4)) and (Equation (3.9)) becomes,

$$\wp((n-1)^2 \vartheta^3 \overset{\circ}{0}) = \wp\left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \frac{\overset{\circ}{0}}{(n-1)\vartheta^3}\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \limsup_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, f\mathfrak{a}_{w_{k+1}}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z_{k+1}}) \right) \\
 &\leq \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \limsup_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b (F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{w_k}), F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{w_k}), \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{z_k})) \right) \\
 &\leq \limsup_{z \rightarrow \infty} \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b (F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{w_k}), F(\mathfrak{a}_{w_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{w_k}), \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_{z_k}, \mathfrak{c}_{z_k})) \right) \\
 &\leq \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \delta \right) - \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \delta \right) \\
 &< \varphi \left((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \delta \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

It is a contradiction. Thus, in $f(\mathfrak{J})$, $\{f\mathfrak{a}_z\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. In a similar manner, we may verify $\{f\mathfrak{c}_z\}$ in $f(\mathfrak{J})$ is a Cauchy sequence. There exists α, β and d, n in \mathfrak{J} such that $f(\mathfrak{J})$ is complete. $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} f\mathfrak{a}_z = \alpha = fd$, $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} f\mathfrak{c}_z = \beta = fn$

Since $f\mathfrak{a}_z \rightarrow \alpha$, $f\mathfrak{c}_z \rightarrow \beta$ for infinitely many z

Now we claim that for $f\mathfrak{a}_z \neq \alpha$, $f\mathfrak{c}_z \neq \beta$

$$\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})) \end{array} \right\} \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{B}, f\mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})) \end{array} \right\}$$

For all $\mathfrak{B}, Z \in \mathfrak{J}$ with $fd \neq f\mathfrak{B}$, $fn \neq fZ$

Let $\mathfrak{B}, Z \in \mathfrak{J}$ with $fd \neq f\mathfrak{B}$, $fn \neq fZ$. Then There exists a positive integer z_0 such that for $z \geq z_0$, suppose that

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}) < \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1})$$

Or

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}) < \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+2})$$

And

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_z, f\mathfrak{c}_z, \dots, fZ) < \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_z, f\mathfrak{c}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1})$$

Or

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1}, \dots, fZ) < \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{c}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{c}_{z+2})$$

Then, using the fact that

$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+2}) \leq \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1})$ we have

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{c}_z)) = \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1})$$

$$\leq (n-1)\vartheta \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}) + \vartheta \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{B})$$

$$\leq \frac{(n-1)}{n\vartheta} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1})$$

$$+ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+2})$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{\vartheta} \left(\frac{n-1}{n} + \frac{1}{n-1} \right) \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1})$$

$$< \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{c}_z))$$

Since the inequality mentioned above is contradictory, we must have that

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\alpha_{z+1}) \leq \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\beta) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\beta), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)) \end{array} \right\}$$

Or

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, f\alpha_{z+2}) \leq \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, f\beta) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, f\beta), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, F(\alpha_{z+1}, \alpha_{z+1})), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_{z+1}, \dots, F(\alpha_{z+1}, \alpha_{z+1})) \end{array} \right\}$$

Hence, from (Equation (3.2)), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z), F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z), \dots, F(\beta, Z))) &\leq \varphi((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z), F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z), \dots, F(\beta, Z))) \\ &\leq \varphi(M(\alpha_z, \alpha_z, \beta, Z)) - \varphi(M(\alpha_z, \alpha_z, \beta, Z)) \\ &\leq \varphi(M(\alpha_z, \alpha_z, \beta, Z)) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$M(\alpha_z, \alpha_z, \beta, Z) = \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(x, y)), \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha_z, f\alpha_z, \dots, F(y, x)) \end{array} \right\}$$

By using the notion of \boxtimes and letting $z \rightarrow \infty$ in the inequality above, we obtain

$$\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\beta, Z)) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right\}$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \leq \max \left(\begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right)$$

Thus

$$\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right\} \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right\}$$

Hence, the claim. Now consider

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)) &\leq (n-1)\vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta) + \vartheta^2 \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\beta, Z)) \\ &\leq n\vartheta^2 \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \beta)) \end{array} \right\}.$$

Hence, from (Equation (3.2)), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \wp(\tilde{n}_b(F(d, n), F(d, n), \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z))) &\leq \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(d, n), F(d, n), \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z))) \\ &\leq \wp(M(d, n, \mathfrak{B}, Z)) - \wp(M(d, n, \mathfrak{B}, Z)) \\ &\leq \wp \left(\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{B}, f\mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{B}, f\mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\} \right) \end{aligned}$$

By the definition of \wp , we have that

$$\tilde{n}_b(F(d, n), F(d, n), \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{B}, f\mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{B}, f\mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fZ, fZ, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Now, from Lemma (2.6), we have

$$\frac{1}{\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, (fd)_{n-1}, F(d, n)) \leq \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, F(d, n))$$

Now from (Equation (3.2)) and applying \wp on both sides, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n))) &\leq \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, f\mathfrak{a}_{z+1}, \dots, F(d, n))) \leq \\ \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z), F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z), \dots, F(d, n))) & \\ \leq \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z, d, n)) - \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z, d, n)) & \\ \text{Here } \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z, d, n)) & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, fn), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z)), \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \dots, \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(d, n)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ &\leq \limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(d, n)), \\ &\frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\mathfrak{a}_z, f\mathfrak{a}_z, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ &\leq \max \{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \} \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^4 \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n))) &\leq \wp \left(\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\} \right) \\ - \liminf_{z \rightarrow \infty} \wp(M(\mathfrak{a}_z, \mathfrak{a}_z, d, n)) & \\ \leq \wp \left(\max \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{aligned} \right\} \right) & \end{aligned}$$

by the definition of φ , one can get that

$$\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3 \vartheta^4} \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \right\}$$

Similarly, we can have

$$\tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3 \vartheta^4} \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \right\}$$

Thus

$$\max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \right\} \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3 \vartheta^4} \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)) \right\}.$$

In order for $F(d, n) = fd$ and $F(n, d) = fn$ to be true. As a result the coupled coincidence point of F & f is (d, n) given that the pair (F, f) is ω -compatible, so

$$f\alpha = f^2d = f(F(d, n)) = F(fd, fn) = F(\alpha, \beta) \text{ and } f\beta = f^2n = f(F(n, d)) = F(fn, fd) = F(\beta, \alpha) \tag{3.10}$$

$$\text{Now } \frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)) = 0 \leq \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\alpha), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, f\beta), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha)) \right\}.$$

From (Equation (3.2)), There is

$$\varphi((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd)) = \varphi((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \beta), F(\alpha, \beta), \dots, F(d, n)))$$

$$\leq \varphi(M(\alpha, \beta, d, n)) - \varphi(M(\alpha, \beta, d, n))$$

$$\leq \varphi(M(\alpha, \beta, d, n))$$

$$\leq \varphi \left(\max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn), \\ \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha)), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(d, n)), \\ \frac{1}{(n-1)\vartheta^3} \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(n, d)) \end{array} \right\} \right)$$

$$\leq \varphi(\max (b\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), b\tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn))).$$

From the property of φ , It has

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3 \vartheta^5} \max (\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn)).$$

Similarly,

$$\tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3 \vartheta^5} \max (\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn)).$$

Thus

$$\max(\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn)) \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^5} \max\left\{\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, fd), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, fn)\right\}.$$

Therefore, the expressions $\beta = fn = f\beta, \alpha = fd = f\alpha$. Therefore, (α, β) is a Coupled Common Fixed Point of F and f as determined by (Equation (3.10)), we will demonstrate the unique coupled common fixed point in \mathfrak{J} in the sections that follow.

Assume that

F, f has another coupled fixed point (α', β') . Now think about,

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)) = 0 \leq \max\left\{\tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, f\alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, f\beta'), \tilde{n}_b(f\alpha, f\alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(f\beta, f\beta, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha))\right\}$$

by (Equation (3.2)), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \wp((n-1)^3\vartheta^6\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha')) &= \wp((n-1)^3\vartheta^6\tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \beta), F(\alpha, \beta), \dots, F(\alpha', \beta'))) \\ &\leq \wp(\max\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta')\}). \end{aligned}$$

Then we have

$$\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha') \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta')\}.$$

Similarly, we can show that

$$\tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta') \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta')\}.$$

Thus

$$\max\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta')\} \leq \frac{1}{(n-1)^3\vartheta^6} \max\left\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \alpha'), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, \beta')\right\}.$$

Therefore $\beta = \beta', \alpha = \alpha'$. The Unique Common Coupled Fixed Point of F and f is hence (α, β)

Case (ii): If $f\alpha_z = f\alpha_{z+1}, f\alpha_z = f\alpha_{z+1}$ for some z then

$f\alpha_z = F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z), f\alpha_z = F(\alpha_z, \alpha_z)$ so that (α_z, α_z) is the coupled coincidence point of F & f . Moreover, following as in case (i) with $f\alpha_z = \alpha, f\alpha_z = \beta$, we can show that (α, β) is the Unique Common Coupled Fixed Point of F & f

Corollary 3.6: Suppose $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be the A_b -metric space and $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ & $F : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ be two mappings which satisfy (φ, \wp) -type contraction with

- a) $F(\mathfrak{J}^2) \subseteq f(\mathfrak{J})$ & $f(I)$ is complete,
- b) (F, f) is ω -compatible.

Following which, we have a Unique Common Coupled Fixed Point of F and f in \mathfrak{J} .

Corollary 3.7: Let $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ be a complete A_b -Metric Space. Suppose that the mapping $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ satisfying (φ, \wp) -type Suzuki contraction, for all $\alpha, \beta, d \in \mathfrak{J}$

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)) \leq \max\left\{\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \beta), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, d), \tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha))\right\} \text{ implies}$$

$$\wp((n-1)^3\vartheta^6\tilde{n}_b(F(\alpha, \beta), F(\alpha, \beta), \dots, F(\beta, d))) \leq \wp(M(\alpha, \beta, d)) - \varphi(M(\alpha, \beta, d))$$

$$\text{where } M(\alpha, \beta, d) = \max\left\{\begin{aligned} &\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, \beta), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, d), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(\alpha, \alpha, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, F(\beta, d)), \tilde{n}_b(d, d, \dots, F(d, \beta)), \\ &\tilde{n}_b(\beta, \beta, \dots, F(\alpha, \beta)), \tilde{n}_b(d, d, \dots, F(\beta, \alpha)) \end{aligned}\right\}$$

Then there is a Unique Fixed Point of F in \mathfrak{J} .

Example 3.8: Suppose $\mathfrak{J} = [0, +\infty)$ we define $\tilde{n}_b : \mathfrak{J}^n \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ as $\tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_1, \mathfrak{a}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{a}_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{i < j} |\mathfrak{a}_i - \mathfrak{a}_j|^2 \forall \mathfrak{a}_i \in \mathfrak{J}, i = 1, 2, \dots$

Following which $(\mathfrak{J}, \tilde{n}_b)$ is a complete A_b -Metric Space with $\vartheta = 2$

Let $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ and $f : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ be given by $F(d, n) = \sin(\frac{6d-3n+72n-3}{72n})$, $f(d) = \frac{2d+3n-2}{3n}$ and $\wp, \varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by $\wp(t) = t$, $\varphi(t) = \frac{t}{2}$, Then clearly, $F(\mathfrak{J}^2) \subseteq f(\mathfrak{J})$ & (F, f) are

ω -compatible & for every $d, n, Z, \mathfrak{B} \in \mathfrak{J}$

$$\frac{1}{8} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)) \leq \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)).$$

$$\leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, f\mathfrak{B}), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, fZ), \\ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(d, n)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(n, d)), \end{array} \right\}$$

Now we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \wp((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(d, n), F(d, n), \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z))) \\ &= (n-1)^4 \vartheta^6 |F(d, n) - F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)|^2 \\ &= (n-1)^4 \vartheta^6 \left| \sin\left(\frac{6d-3n+72n-3}{72n}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{6\mathfrak{B}-3Z+72n-3}{72n}\right) \right|^2 \\ &= 4(n-1)^4 \vartheta^6 \left| \cos\left(\frac{6d-3n+144n-6+6\mathfrak{B}-3Z}{72n}\right) \sin\left(\frac{6d-3n-6\mathfrak{B}+3Z}{72n}\right) \right|^2 \\ &\leq 4(n-1)^4 \vartheta^6 \left| \frac{6d-3n-6\mathfrak{B}+3Z+144n-6}{72n} \right|^2 \\ &\leq \frac{(n-1)}{4} \left(\left| \frac{2d+3n-2}{3n} - \sin\left(\frac{6\mathfrak{B}-3Z+72n-2}{72n}\right) \right|^2 + \left| \frac{2n+3n-2}{3n} - \sin\left(\frac{6Z-3\mathfrak{B}+72n-2}{72n}\right) \right|^2 \right) \\ &\leq \frac{(n-1)}{4} (|fd - F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)|^2 + |fn - F(Z, \mathfrak{B})|^2) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (\tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)) + \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B}))) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \max \{ \tilde{n}_b(fd, fd, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(fn, fn, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})) \} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} M(d, n, \mathfrak{B}, Z) \leq \wp(M(d, n, \mathfrak{B}, Z)) - \varphi(M(d, n, \mathfrak{B}, Z)) \end{aligned}$$

Plug in $n = 2$ and $\vartheta = 2$ this satisfies all the requirements of the **Theorem 3.5** and $(1, 1)$ is the only unique coupled common fixed point of F and f .

4 Application to Integral Equations

As an application to **Corollary 3.7** we examine the existence of a unique solution to an initial value problem in this section
Theorem 4.1. Take into consideration the initial value problem

$$\mathfrak{B}^1(t) = T(t, (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(t)), t \in I = [0, 1], (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(0) = (\mathfrak{B}_0, Z_0) \tag{4.1}$$

Here $T : I \times R \rightarrow R$ along with $\int_0^t T(s, (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(s))ds = \max \left\{ \int_0^t T(s, (\mathfrak{B}(s)))ds, \int_0^t T(s, (Z(s)))ds \right\}$
 & $\mathfrak{B}_0, Z_0 \in R$. Then there exists unique solution for the initial value problem (Equation (4.1)) in $C(I, R)$

Proof. Corresponding integral equation for the initial value problem (Equation (4.1)) is

$$\mathfrak{B}(t) = \mathfrak{B}_0 + \frac{\sqrt{(n-1)^3}}{2} \vartheta^5 \int_0^t T(s, (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(s))ds.$$

Let $\mathfrak{J} = C(I, R)$ and $\tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{a}_1, \mathfrak{a}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{a}_{n-1}, \mathfrak{a}_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{i < j} |\mathfrak{a}_i - \mathfrak{a}_j|^2$ to each $\mathfrak{a}_i \in \mathfrak{J}, i = 1, 2, \dots$ define $F : \mathfrak{J}^2 \rightarrow \mathfrak{J}$ by

$$F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)(t) = \frac{2\mathfrak{B}_0}{\sqrt{(n-1)^3} \vartheta^5} + \int_0^t T(s, (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(s))ds.$$

and $\varphi, \varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ as $\varphi(t) = t$ & $\varphi(t) = \frac{3t}{4}$. Clearly, for all $\mathfrak{B}, Z \in \mathfrak{J}$, we have

$$\frac{1}{n\vartheta^2} \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)) \leq \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{B}, \dots, d), \tilde{n}_b(Z, Z, \dots, n), \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{B}, \dots, F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)), \tilde{n}_b(Z, Z, \dots, F(Z, \mathfrak{B})) \right\}.$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi((n-1)^3 \vartheta^6 \tilde{n}_b(F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)(t), F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)(t), \dots, F(d, n)(t))) &= (n-1)^4 \vartheta^6 |F(\mathfrak{B}, Z)(t) - F(d, n)(t)|^2 \\ &= \left| \frac{2\mathfrak{B}_0}{\sqrt{(n-1)^3} \vartheta^5} + \int_0^t T(s, (\mathfrak{B}, Z)(s))ds - \frac{2\mathfrak{B}_0}{\sqrt{(n-1)^3} \vartheta^5} + \int_0^t T(s, (d, n)(s))ds \right|^2 \\ &\leq \frac{4(n-1)}{\vartheta^4} \max\{|\mathfrak{B}(t) - d(t)|^2, |Z(t) - n(t)|^2\} = \frac{1}{4} \max \left\{ \tilde{n}_b(\mathfrak{B}, \mathfrak{B}, \dots, d), \tilde{n}_b(Z, Z, \dots, n) \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4} M(\mathfrak{B}, Z, d, n) \leq \varphi(M(\mathfrak{B}, Z, d, n)) - \varphi(M(\mathfrak{B}, Z, d, n)) \end{aligned}$$

Based on **Corollary 3.7**, we can infer that there is only one fixed point for F in \mathfrak{J} .

5 Conclusion

We proved the existence and uniqueness of a common coupled fixed-point for two mappings in the setup of complete A_b -metric space, via (φ, φ) -type Suzuki contraction with an example. And also illustrated the application to integral equations.

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